

**INTERNATIONAL
ONLINE SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE**

**GlobalMed 2026:
Multidisciplinary Advances in
Modern Medicine**

January 30, 2026

Turkey

CONTENTS

Michael Eisenhut	ACQUIRED CYSTIC FIBROSIS TRANSMEMBRANE CONDUCTANCE REGULATOR DYSFUNCTION	3
Swati Rai	INTEGRATING MULTI-OMICS AND MACHINE LEARNING FOR SUBTYPE- SPECIFIC RISK STRATIFICATION IN BREAST CANCER: A STEP TOWARD PERSONALIZED PREVENTIVE MEDICINE	4
Sobirova Dildora	PULMONARY VASCULAR WALL CHARACTERISTICS IN EXPERIMENTAL DIABETES MELLITUS	6
Qin Xie, Li Liu	SPECIALIZED INTERVENTIONAL CARE FOR MASSIVE ESOPHAGOGASTRIC VARICEAL BLEEDING IN DECOMPENSATED CIRRHOSIS: A MIDLIFE CASE STUDY	9
Hala M. Alzeer, Fadi G. Saqallah	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MELANOMA: INTEGRATING MULTI-OMICS DATA FOR PRECISION ONCOLOGY AND PERSONALIZED GENE THERAPY	11
Pellegrino Mazzone, Giuseppina Di Paola, Daniele Bravoco, Teresa D'Amore, Francesco Albano, Geppino Falco	A NOVEL MOLECULAR MECHANISM REGULATES GASTRIC CANCER CELL HOMEOSTASIS	13
Akhrorova Laylo Barnoyevna	IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHOD OF PROCESSING THE RESIDUAL SPACE AFTER ECHINOCOCCETOMY IN MULTIPLE AND RECURRENT LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS	15
Yao Wei, Uliano Guerrini, Ivano Eberini	STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS INTO CYP3A4-P- GP INTERACTIONS AND THEIR ROLE IN PERSONALIZED AUTOIMMUNE DRUG THERAPY	19
Khamidova Nodira	NEUROCOGNITIVE AND EMOTIONAL HEALTH IN PEDIATRIC PATIENTS WITH JUVENILE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS	21

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHOD OF PROCESSING THE RESIDUAL SPACE AFTER ECHINOCOCECTOMY IN MULTIPLE AND RECURRENT LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS

Akhrorova Laylo Barnoyevna

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

The numerous complications of the disease, the unsatisfactory results of intraoperative use of germicidal drugs (high toxicity, insufficient germicidal activity), their prolonged exposure during surgery, and sometimes the need to repeat the procedures many times, forced the search for new methods of treating cysts (Karimov Sh.I., 2018; Sharipov U.B., 2012). The effectiveness of treatment measures is determined not only by the rationality of preoperative preparation, surgical intervention and postoperative treatment, but also by the use of effective methods to reduce the cost of complications in clinical practice and their prevention (Khodzhimatov G.M., 2020; Cherkasov M.F., 2016).

Scientific research is being conducted extensively around the world to prevent complications after hepatic echinococcectomy, but scientists emphasize that improving the results of treating this disease can be achieved not only by improving surgical procedures and prescribing antiparasitic chemotherapeutic drugs to these patients in the postoperative period, but also by using an optimal method of treating the residual space after hepatic echinococcectomy (Babadzhanov A.Kh., 2020; Makhmudov U.M., 2019).

Taking into account the above, the development of methods with effective antiparasitic effect on parasitic elements in the liver fibrous capsule layer after multiple and recurrent liver echinococcectomy remains one of the urgent problems of medicine today.

The purpose of the study: to reduce the complication of echinococcal recurrence by betadine -assisted laser photodynamic therapy of the residual cavity after

echinococcectomy in recurrent and multiple hepatic echinococcosis

Materials and methods of the study: The study included 95 patients treated with multiple and recurrent hepatic echinococcosis at the Bukhara Regional Multi-disciplinary Medical Center during 2019-2024 . When analyzing the age and gender composition of patients, it was found that 52 (54.7%) of them were women and 43 (45.3%) were men (Figure 2.1). According to the results of the analysis, multiple and recurrent forms of hepatic echinococcosis were mainly found in patients of working age (18–59 years), who accounted for 80.9% of the total contingent.

Results and their analysis: During the study, a total of 95 patients were involved in clinical observation and analysis, of which 50 patients formed the control group and 45 patients formed the main group. In patients in the control group, the residual space after liver echinococcectomy was treated in the usual way (with hydrogen peroxide, iodine, alcohol solutions) and changes in immunological indicators were studied. The main group of patients were divided into 2 subgroups. In group IIA, the residual space after liver echinococcectomy was treated with Betadine (Povidone-iodine) solution, and in group IIB, the photosensitizer Betadine (Povidone-iodine) solution and low-intensity laser light (LILN) were used as an antiparasitic scolecicidal agent on the residual space after liver echinococcectomy.

A total of 50 patients in the control group were treated surgically according to the standard recommended method. Among them, the most frequently used method was semi-closed echinococcectomy of the right lobe of the liver, which was performed in 29 patients (58.0%). The second place is semi-closed echinococcectomy of the left lobe of the liver, which was performed in 6 patients (12.0%). This result shows that the left lobe of the liver is less affected by the process of echinococcosis. Simultaneous semi-closed echinococcectomy of the right and left lobes of the liver was also performed in 4 patients (8.0%). These cases are associated with the simultaneous involvement of multiple cysts in two lobes, which increases the complexity and volume of the operation.

A total of 45 patients in the main group underwent various surgical operations. Their structural analysis shows that the surgical tactics used in hepatic echinococcosis were mainly determined by the localization, multiplicity and concomitant lesions of the disease.

The most frequently performed surgical procedure in the main group was semi-closed echinococcectomy of the right lobe of the liver, which was performed in 23 patients (51.1%). This indicator once again confirms that the right lobe of the liver is more susceptible to the process of echinococcosis. In second place was semi-closed echinococcectomy of the left lobe of the liver (8.9%; 4 patients).

As a result of the study, specific postoperative complications were noted in 23 patients (46.0%) in the control group, the main part of which was wound complications (24.0%) and problems with the residual space (22.0%). In particular, suppuration (10.0%), purulent abscesses (6.0%) and seromas (8.0%) were more common. Among the residual space complications, the most frequently observed cases were long-term purulent abscesses (10.0%) and biliary abscesses (6.0%).

In the main group, these indicators decreased significantly. Specific complications were noted in 6 patients (13.3%), including suppuration (4.4%), purulent fistula (2.2%), and biliary fistula (4.4%). Seromas and purulent infection of the residual space were not observed at all. This indicates the effectiveness of the integrated approach and optimized surgical tactics used to prevent complications.

The analysis of general complications also shows a significant difference between the groups. In the control group, they were recorded in 8 cases (16.0%), including acute liver failure (6.0%), pleuropneumonia (4.0%), cardiovascular failure (4.0%), and one death (2.0%). In the main group, general complications were limited to 2 cases (6.7%): pleuropneumonia (4.4%) and cardiovascular failure (2.2%).

Summary. From the obtained results, it can be seen that postoperative compli-

cations in the main group were significantly less than in the control group. It was noted that specific complications decreased by 3.5 times, and general complications decreased by 2.4 times. These are the complex surgical tactics used and confirms the effectiveness of individual preventive measures.

**“GLOBALMED 2026: MULTIDISCIPLINARY
ADVANCES IN MODERN MEDICINE”**

International Online Scientific Conference

CERTIFICATE

AKHROROVA LAYLO BARNOYEVNA

was awarded for his active participation in the scientific work on the topic

*“Improvement of the Method of Processing the
Residual Space After Echinococcectomy in Multiple
and Recurrent Liver Echinococcosis”*

TURKEY, JANUARY 30, 2026

